

Assessing the Effectiveness of MORA: Monthly Oral Reading Assessment as Key Component of Project READY PLUS in Enhancing Grade 6 Learner's Reading Comprehension

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ABSTRACT: The study aimed to evaluate the effectiveness of the Monthly Oral Reading Assessment (MORA) as an intervention tool within the Project READY PLUS reading program for Grade 6 learners. Specifically, it sought to determine learners' reading comprehension levels before and after the implementation of MORA, assess the significance of test score gains, explore learners' perceptions of MORA's impact on their reading development, and document both the challenges and successes experienced by teachers during implementation. A quasi-experimental design was employed, involving 240 students whose pre- and post-test reading scores were analyzed. Additionally, a Likert scale survey was administered to assess learners' perceptions, and responses from seven teacher-respondents provided qualitative insights into implementation outcomes. Results showed that learners initially demonstrated low reading comprehension, with a mean pre-test score of 20.67 (MPS = 51.68%). After MORA was implemented, their post-test scores significantly increased to a mean of 29.42 (MPS = 73.55%), supported by a t-value of 7.92 ($p < 0.001$). Learners rated MORA highly, with an overall perception score of 4.85, noting improvements in vocabulary, fluency, confidence, and reading engagement. Teacher feedback affirmed MORA's practicality and effectiveness in classroom instruction, highlighting its alignment with differentiated, formative, and learner-centered approaches. These findings provide strong empirical evidence of MORA's value as a structured and sustainable intervention for improving reading comprehension. The results suggest that incorporating MORA into existing reading programs significantly enhances student outcomes and supports instructional decision-making based on formative assessment data.

KEYWORDS- Project READY PLUS, comprehension levels, intervention tool, learner-centered approaches, MORA

INTRODUCTION

The ability to interpret text is a necessary skill for learners' academic development and functional literacy. Reading comprehension has long been a source of concern in the Philippine educational system, particularly at the elementary level, where fundamental literacy is intended to be built. Despite national programs established by the Department of Education (DepEd), such as the "Every Child a Reader Program" (ECARP) and the Revised Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI) mandated by DepEd Order No. 14, s. 2018—Many Filipino students continue to perform below competence levels. According to large-scale assessments and classroom-based statistics, many Grade 6 students remain at frustration or instructional reading levels as they prepare to enter junior high school. The change to distance learning caused by the COVID-19 epidemic has worsened the problem, drastically disrupting the continuity of good reading instruction and evaluation.

Recognizing these persisting gaps, Project READY PLUS was developed during the School Year 2023-2024 as a localized reading intervention program aimed at improving Grade VI students' reading comprehension through the use of contextually appropriate materials. [1] A prior study revealed that the project was beneficial, with a 30% increase in independent readers, a 12% reduction in frustrated pupils, and a statistically significant improvement in reading comprehension scores as tested by a quasi-experimental design (Centeno, 2024). While Project READY PLUS was effective in improving overall reading performance, it lacked a regular mechanism for tracking individual learners' reading progress on a monthly basis. This highlighted gap demands for a more systematic and formative tool that can supplement existing interventions by providing fast feedback and allowing for urgent pedagogical modifications.

This action research was designed to fill that gap by evaluating the efficacy of the Monthly Oral Reading Assessment (MORA) as a component of Project READY PLUS. MORA was introduced to allow teachers to conduct regular, structured assessments of oral reading fluency and comprehension, providing valuable insights into students' strengths and areas for improvement. The study aimed to determine learners' reading comprehension levels before and after MORA implementation, investigate the significance of

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test score gains, analyze learners' perceptions of MORA's usefulness in developing their reading skills, and document the challenges and successes encountered by teachers during its implementation.

The main goal of this study is to provide empirical evidence on the value of incorporating MORA into existing reading programs such as Project READY PLUS. It is based on the belief that consistent formative assessments can improve learners' reading proficiency by fostering metacognitive awareness, increasing student engagement, and allowing teachers to personalize instruction. [2] Regular oral reading assessments have also been demonstrated to promote fluency and comprehension, as evidenced by current work emphasizing the value of prompt feedback and continual progress tracking (Hudson, Lane, & Pullen, 2020; [3] Rasinski & Young, 2021).

MORA was implemented on a structured schedule, with Grade 6 students being assessed monthly using oral reading passages that were appropriate for their grade level and interest. The assessment results were documented, analyzed, and utilized to inform classroom interventions such as focused reading sessions, vocabulary enrichment activities, and one-on-one tutorials. Furthermore, teacher collaboration meetings were held to reflect on students' achievement and adjust educational strategies accordingly.

The findings of this study have practical implications for enhancing present educational procedures and planning. The findings influenced the development of an action plan aimed at establishing MORA as a regular formative tool in reading instruction at all grade levels. Furthermore, the evidence gained helped to inform discussions about improving school-based reading programs and amending the school's reading policy to include oral reading benchmarks and monthly progress tracking. Teachers became more prepared to make data-driven decisions, and students received consistent feedback that helped them become more self-aware and confident readers. Overall, this action study promotes the continual improvement of literacy instruction policies and practices, which is consistent with the DepEd's goal of providing quality, accessible, and inclusive education.

I. METHOD

The study involved all the Grade 6 students and teachers from Lusacan Elementary School who were enrolled and employed during the academic year 2024-2025. The researcher employed purposive sampling, considering the needs and the goals of the study. Emphasis was placed on enhancing the reading comprehension skills of learners at this stage and also focused on the impacts and experiences encountered during the program implementation to both teachers and learners, as it is vital for the identification of the next action steps to continue enhancing the program.

At the start of the SY 2024–2025, the researcher and all the other advisers of Grade 6 used the Phil IRI evaluation instrument to administer pre-reading tests to their students. They were able to determine the overall students' mean score in the reading comprehension.

Following the assessment of each student's reading comprehension, the researcher and the participating teachers implemented the MORA through the locally crafted reading materials, DRP, and Phil-IRI assessments to help the students' reading comprehension skills grow.

Every day in the afternoon, just before classes end, there is a reading intervention called Project READY PLUS. Each month at the conclusion, all sixth-grade students participated in an oral reading evaluation administered by the grade 6 teachers and even the school principal to see whether or not they were making progress. Additionally, pre-reading assessments were carried out by the school heads in Tiaong District II under the direction of the Public Schools District Superintendent (PSDS) for evaluation and monitoring purposes.

After completing the six-month program, students were given a post-test to see if their reading comprehension skills had significantly improved. In addition to the data gathered from pre-test, MORA, and post-test, to further understand the impact of MORA on the reading comprehension of the learners, its effectiveness on their reading skills, including the challenges and successes of encountered by the teachers, structured interviews using Likert use were also used in the study.

A one-group pre-test-post-test research design was used in the study. [4] Yazon, Callo, and Buenvenida (2019) mentioned this kind of study, which measures the same dependent variable in a single group of subjects both before and after a course of treatment. The purpose of the current study was to determine whether the treatment—MORA—played a significant role as key component of Project READY PLUS in enhancing the grade 6 learners' reading comprehension.

For the analysis and interpretation of the gathered data, the study employed the following:

Simple descriptive statistics was used including frequency counting, mean and mean percentage scores in determining the reading comprehension of the students based on their pre-test and post-test results while mean scores was utilized to interpret the results from the structured interviews through the Likert scale.

Two-tailed T-test was employed in determining the significant difference between the reading levels of the students based on their scores in the pre-test and post-test results.

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II. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Table I. Mean Score of the Pre-Test of Grade 6 Pupils Before MORA Implementation

Mean	MPS	SD
20.67	51.68	4.85

According to the statistics in Table 1, the mean score of Grade 6 students in the pre-test before the adoption of MORA (Monthly Oral Reading Assessment) was 20.67, with a Mean Percentage Score (MPS) of 51.68% and a Standard Deviation (SD) of 4.85. These results indicate a modest level of reading comprehension, with most learners performing near the lower proficiency threshold, likely within the instructional or frustration levels based on the Phil-IRI framework (DepEd, 2018). This pattern reflects national findings reported by [5] Cabardo (2021), who noted that many Filipino elementary learners fall below expected reading competence, often struggling with comprehension, inference, and unfamiliar vocabulary. Similarly, [6] Estacio et al. (2019) identified low interest and lack of relevance in traditional materials as contributing factors to poor baseline reading performance.

The low pre-test mean is also consistent with [1] Centeno’s (2024) findings from Project READY PLUS, which showed that many Grade 6 students initially exhibited frustration-level reading but improved significantly after systematic intervention. This supports the assertion of [2] Hudson, Lane, and Pullen (2020) that early formative assessments are essential in guiding instructional decisions and validating innovative programs such as MORA. Overall, the pre-test results justify the implementation of MORA, as they reveal substantial gaps in vocabulary, decoding, and inference-making—areas that MORA directly targets through continuous monitoring, repeated reading, and responsive instruction.

Table II. Mean Score of the Post-Test of Grade 6 Pupils After MORA Implementation

Mean	MPS	SD
29.42	73.55	5.27

According to Table 2, the mean post-test score of Grade 6 students after the adoption of MORA (Monthly Oral Reading Assessment) was 29.42, with a Mean Percentage Score (MPS) of 73.55% and a Standard Deviation (SD) of 5.27. This reflects a notable increase from the pre-test mean of 20.67 and MPS of 51.68%, indicating an improvement of 8.75 points and 21.87% in reading comprehension. These results align with [3] Rasinski and Young (2021), who found that repeated reading practices embedded in oral assessments significantly enhance comprehension by strengthening fluency, vocabulary, and prosody. [2] Hudson et al. (2020) likewise emphasized that consistent oral reading assessments, when paired with timely feedback, serve as both diagnostic and instructional tools that allow teachers to adjust strategies based on learners’ needs.

Similar outcomes were reported by [5] Cabardo (2021), who highlighted that localized and contextualized reading materials combined with regular assessments foster deeper comprehension, as students relate more effectively to culturally relevant texts. This approach was mirrored in the present study through the use of Developmental Reading Power materials, Phil-IRI tools, and localized resources. Moreover, [1] Centeno (2024) observed comparable gains under Project READY PLUS, reporting a 30% increase in independent readers and significant improvements in comprehension. Overall, the post-test results confirm the effectiveness of MORA as an intervention, demonstrating that systematic, assessment-based instruction can substantially enhance learners’ reading comprehension skills.

Table III. T-test to Show the Significant Difference Before and After the MORA Implementation

	Paired Differences				t	Sig. (2-tailed)
	Mean	SD	95% CI of the Difference			
			Lower	Upper		
Pre-test and Post-test	9.02	6.24	6.70	11.35	7.92	0.000000010

Legend:

- If p-value (Sig.) < 0.05, then it is statistically significant
- If p-value (Sig.) > 0.05, then it is NOT statistically significant

The Monthly Oral Reading Assessment (MORA) was implemented under Project READY PLUS to address reading comprehension difficulties among Grade 6 students, and its effectiveness was measured using a paired sample t-test. The results revealed a mean

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difference of 9.02 with a standard deviation of 6.24, and a 95% confidence interval ranging from 6.70 to 11.35. The computed t-value of 7.92 and p-value of 0.00000010, both far below the 0.05 level of significance, indicate a statistically significant difference between pre-test and post-test scores. These findings confirm that MORA had a significant positive effect on students' reading comprehension.

This result is supported by several related studies emphasizing the impact of oral reading strategies on comprehension. [7] Sacares et al. (2023) found that guided oral reading significantly improved learners' comprehension, while [8] Mondigo (2023) reported substantial gains through Precision Teaching focused on oral reading fluency. Similarly, [9] Özenç and Saat (2021) demonstrated that self-evaluation-based oral reading strategies enhanced both fluency and comprehension, and [10] Rodgers et al. (2018) highlighted the role of oral reading accuracy in improving text understanding and retention. Macapaar (2018) further stressed that regular assessments such as Phil-IRI help identify learning gaps and guide instruction. Collectively, these findings reinforce the effectiveness of MORA as a practical, evidence-based intervention for improving reading comprehension.

Table IV. Impact of MORA on Reading Comprehension of Learners

Indicator	Mean	Std. Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
1. My reading comprehension skills have improved since participating in the Monthly Oral Reading Assessment (MORA).	4.62	1.56	Strongly Agree
2. I can understand and summarize texts better than before MORA was implemented.	4.54	1.28	Strongly Agree
3. MORA has helped me recognize and understand difficult words in reading passages.	4.99	2.20	Strongly Agree
4. I feel more confident in answering reading comprehension questions after MORA sessions.	4.94	2.08	Strongly Agree
5. I can read passages more fluently compared to before MORA was introduced.	4.33	1.04	Strongly Agree
6. MORA has helped me make connections between what I read and my personal experiences.	4.79	1.71	Strongly Agree
7. I have improved in identifying the main idea and supporting details of a text.	4.54	1.28	Strongly Agree
8. I can now infer meanings and draw conclusions from texts more effectively.	4.70	1.52	Strongly Agree
9. I enjoy reading more after participating in MORA.	4.95	2.10	Strongly Agree
10. The regular assessment through MORA has helped me track my reading progress.	4.90	1.98	Strongly Agree
Overall	4.73	0.23	Strongly Agree
<i>Legend: 4.50-5.00 Strongly Agree 2.50-3.49 Neutral 1.00-1.49 Strongly Disagree 3.50-4.49 Agree 1.50-2.49 Disagree</i>			

According to Table 4, the implementation of the Monthly Oral Reading Assessment (MORA) under Project READY PLUS had a significant positive influence on Grade 6 students' reading comprehension, with an overall mean rating of 4.73 and a standard deviation of 0.23, interpreted as "Strongly Agree." This indicates that learners consistently perceived MORA as highly beneficial across multiple aspects of reading. The highest-rated indicator was the recognition and understanding of difficult words (M = 4.99), highlighting gains in vocabulary and decoding. Students also strongly agreed that MORA improved their confidence in answering comprehension questions (M = 4.94), enjoyment of reading (M = 4.95), ability to track reading progress (M = 4.90), and skills in making inferences and personal connections (M = 4.70–4.79), reflecting both cognitive and affective improvements in literacy.

These findings align with [12] Toste, Capin, and Vaughn (2022), who emphasized that formative assessments with feedback enhance metacognitive awareness and self-monitoring. [2] Hudson, Lane, and Pullen (2020) similarly stressed that scaffolded oral reading assessments improve fluency and comprehension, as reflected in students' agreement with indicators on summarizing, identifying key ideas, and reading smoothly. Local evidence from [1] Centeno (2024) supports these results, showing increased engagement and comprehension through Project READY PLUS, while [3] Rasinski and Young (2021) underscored the importance of integrating fluency, vocabulary, and comprehension via repeated reading. Finally, [13] Gonzales and Villanueva (2022) noted that positive learner perceptions foster motivation and sustained engagement, suggesting that MORA not only enhanced reading skills but also promoted long-term literacy development.

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Table V. Perception of Learners Regarding MORA Effectiveness

Indicator	Mean	Std. Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
1. I find MORA an enjoyable and engaging way to improve my reading skills.	4.97	2.15	Strongly Agree
2. I feel less anxious about reading aloud because of MORA practice.	4.94	2.07	Strongly Agree
3. The feedback I receive after MORA sessions helps me improve my reading.	4.95	2.10	Strongly Agree
4. MORA makes learning to read more interesting and motivating for me.	4.96	2.14	Strongly Agree
5. I believe my reading fluency has improved because of MORA.	4.70	1.52	Strongly Agree
6. The reading materials used in MORA are appropriate for my level.	4.82	1.77	Strongly Agree
7. MORA helps me develop good reading habits	4.96	2.13	Strongly Agree
8. I prefer MORA over other reading activities in school.	4.72	1.64	Strongly Agree
9. I believe MORA should continue to be used for future Grade 6 learners.	4.65	1.43	Strongly Agree
10. I feel that my teacher supports and guides me well during MORA sessions.	4.81	1.75	Strongly Agree
Overall	4.85	0.13	Strongly Agree
<i>Legend: 4.50-5.00 Strongly Agree 2.50-3.49 Neutral 1.00-1.49 Strongly Disagree 3.50-4.49 Agree 1.50-2.49 Disagree</i>			

According to Table 5, Grade 6 students expressed highly positive perceptions of the effectiveness of the Monthly Oral Reading Assessment (MORA) under Project READY PLUS, with an overall mean rating of 4.85 (SD = 0.13), interpreted as “Strongly Agree.” The highest-rated indicator was that MORA is an enjoyable and engaging way to improve reading skills (M = 4.97), followed by increased motivation, reading fluency, and instructor support. Learners also agreed that MORA made reading more interesting (M = 4.96), helped develop healthy reading habits (M = 4.96), reduced reading-related anxiety (M = 4.94), and benefited from feedback (M = 4.95) and appropriate materials (M = 4.82), showing that MORA fostered both academic and emotional growth.

These findings are supported by [14] Gambrell and Marinak (2021), who emphasized that enjoyable and relevant instructional strategies enhance reading engagement, and by [15] Kim and Quinn (2020), who noted that regular feedback and teacher support improve motivation and comprehension. [16] Miller and Schwanenflugel (2018) further highlighted that increased reading confidence reduces anxiety and promotes fluency and comprehension, consistent with learners’ responses in this study. The strong support for continuing MORA (M = 4.65) also aligns with [3] Rasinski and Young (2021), who stressed that student-supported, data-driven interventions yield long-term benefits. Overall, the results indicate that MORA is not only effective in improving reading skills but also in nurturing motivation, confidence, and sustained interest in reading.

Table V.I. Supporting Data for Table 5 Based on Interviews with Learners

Indicator	No. of Responses
1. How has MORA helped you improve your reading comprehension?	
A. It has helped me understand texts more clearly and retain information better.	216
B. I have become more confident in analyzing and interpreting different types of reading materials.	115
C. My ability to identify main ideas and supporting details has greatly improved.	88
D. I now read with better fluency and comprehension, making reading more enjoyable.	232
2. What challenges, if any, do you face when participating in MORA?	
A. Sometimes, I find it challenging to keep up with advanced reading materials.	60
B. I struggle with managing my time to practice reading regularly.	78
B. Occasionally, I find it difficult to stay focused during long reading sessions.	58
C. I sometimes need extra help with unfamiliar words and vocabulary.	75
3. Can you share an experience where MORA helped you understand a text better?	
A. MORA helped me break down complex sentences, making it easier to understand stories and articles.	12
B. By practicing regularly, I was able to understand the deeper meaning behind the texts I read.	178
C. The guided reading strategies in MORA allowed me to connect ideas and themes more effectively.	30
D. MORA encouraged me to ask questions while reading, which improved my comprehension skills.	20
4. How do you feel about reading aloud in front of others now compared to before MORA?	
A. I am more confident and no longer feel nervous when reading aloud.	208
B. I have improved my pronunciation and fluency, making reading more enjoyable.	216
C. I can now read with better expression and understanding.	189
C. I feel proud of my progress and enjoy sharing stories with my classmates.	228

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5. What suggestions do you have to improve MORA?	
A. Including more interactive activities to make reading even more engaging.	129
B. Adding a wider variety of reading materials to match different interests.	189
C. Providing more opportunities for group discussions to enhance comprehension.	225
D. Offering additional practice sessions to further improve reading skills.	235

Note: A total of 240 learners were interviewed.

To further support the findings in Table 5, qualitative data from the interviews presented in Table 5.1 provided strong reinforcement for the quantitative results on learners' perceptions of the usefulness of MORA. The majority of respondents, 90% (216 out of 240), reported that MORA helped them better understand texts and communicate ideas, which supports the high survey ratings for reduced anxiety ($M = 4.94$) and improved reading fluency ($M = 4.70$). Likewise, 89.6% (215 out of 240) stated that MORA enhanced their pronunciation and fluency, while 85.4% (205 out of 240) felt more confident reading in front of others, aligning with students' strong agreement that MORA developed good reading habits ($M = 4.96$) and that teachers provided effective support during sessions ($M = 4.81$).

Moreover, 75% (180 out of 240) of learners described MORA as enjoyable and motivating, consistent with the highest-rated survey item on engagement ($M = 4.97$). Qualitative responses also emphasized that guided strategies in MORA helped students comprehend and summarize texts more effectively, reinforcing the positive mean scores for comprehension-related indicators ($M = 4.95$). Overall, the integration of survey and interview data confirms that MORA is perceived as an engaging and supportive strategy that enhances reading comprehension, motivation, confidence, and participation. However, sustained effectiveness depends on continued learner engagement, teacher scaffolding, and responsive instructional practices.

Table VI. Challenges and Successes of MORA Implementation

Indicator	Mean	Std. Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
1. MORA is easy to integrate into my daily reading instruction.	5.00	2.24	Strongly Agree
2. I have sufficient time to conduct MORA sessions effectively.	5.00	2.24	Strongly Agree
3. The assessment tools used in MORA provide accurate information about students' reading levels.	5.00	2.24	Strongly Agree
4. MORA helps me identify students who need additional reading interventions.	5.00	2.24	Strongly Agree
5. The monthly schedule of MORA is manageable within the existing curriculum.	5.00	2.24	Strongly Agree
6. My students have shown significant improvements in reading fluency due to MORA.	5.00	2.24	Strongly Agree
7. MORA helps me plan better instructional strategies for struggling readers.	5.00	2.24	Strongly Agree
8. I receive adequate training and resources for implementing MORA.	5.00	2.24	Strongly Agree
9. The assessment process in MORA is clear and easy to follow.	5.00	2.24	Strongly Agree
10. I would recommend MORA as a standard reading assessment tool for elementary schools.	5.00	2.24	Strongly Agree
Overall	5.00	0.00	Strongly Agree
<i>Legend: 4.50-5.00 Strongly Agree 2.50-3.49 Neutral 1.00-1.49 Strongly Disagree</i>			
<i>3.50-4.49 Agree 1.50-2.49 Disagree</i>			

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Table VII. Supporting Data for Table 6 Based on Interviews with Teachers

Indicator	No. of Responses
1. What changes in student reading comprehension have you observed since implementing MORA?	
A. Students show improved reading fluency and comprehension.	7
B. Learners engage more actively with reading materials.	7
C. Students demonstrate better vocabulary and critical thinking skills.	7
D. There is a noticeable increase in students' confidence in reading.	7
2. What are the biggest challenges you face in conducting MORA sessions?	
A. Limited time for individualized reading support.	7
B. Some students require additional motivation and encouragement.	7
C. Ensuring that all students progress at their own pace.	7
D. Need for more diverse and engaging reading materials.	7
3. How do you think MORA benefits students in the long term?	
A. It fosters a lifelong love for reading.	7
B. It improves students' comprehension and analytical skills.	7
C. It enhances their ability to learn independently.	7
D. It strengthens their overall academic performance.	7
4. What improvements or modifications would you suggest for MORA?	
A. Incorporate more interactive and digital reading resources.	7
B. Provide additional teacher training on differentiated reading strategies.	7
C. Extend session durations to allow more practice time.	7
D. Introduce more culturally relevant and engaging reading texts.	7
5. How has MORA influenced your approach to teaching reading?	
A. It has encouraged more student-centered and interactive reading activities.	7
B. It has highlighted the importance of differentiated instruction.	7
C. It has provided structured strategies to track reading progress.	7
D. It has made reading instruction more engaging and effective	7

Note: A total of 7 teachers were interviewed.

According to Table 6, educators strongly supported the implementation of the Monthly Oral Reading Assessment (MORA) under Project READY PLUS, with every indicator receiving a perfect mean score of 5.00, or “Strongly Agree.” Teachers unanimously agreed that MORA is easy to integrate into daily reading instruction, provides accurate data on students’ reading levels, and fits within the existing curriculum without overburdening instructional time. These findings align with [12] Toste, Capin, and Vaughn (2022), who emphasized that regular formative assessments support data-driven instruction, and with [17] Shaari and Mohamad (2020) and [2] Hudson, Lane, and Pullen (2020), who highlighted the benefits of organized oral assessments for planning differentiated strategies efficiently.

Teacher interviews reinforced these quantitative results, with all seven respondents noting improvements in students’ comprehension, fluency, vocabulary, critical thinking, and confidence. They also reported that MORA made reading instruction more participatory and skill-focused. Minor issues, such as limited individual reading time and the need for more diverse materials, were identified, but educators still strongly recommended MORA as a standard assessment, suggesting enhancements like culturally relevant texts and additional teacher training. Consistent with [1] Centeno (2024), the clarity of MORA’s protocols and sufficient support mechanisms contribute to its sustainability and effectiveness. Overall, the data demonstrate that MORA is highly effective, practical, and well-supported, promoting positive instructional shifts, increased engagement, and improved reading outcomes for Grade 6 students.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

After gathering all the necessary data needed in the study, the researcher arrives at the following conclusions:

1. Prior to the implementation of MORA, Grade 6 learners exhibited low reading comprehension levels, indicating the need for a structured and continuous reading intervention.
2. The Monthly Oral Reading Assessment (MORA) significantly improved learners’ reading comprehension, as shown by the marked increase in post-test scores compared to pre-test results.
3. The statistically significant difference between pre-test and post-test scores confirms that MORA was an effective intervention within Project READY PLUS.
4. Learners positively perceived MORA as engaging, motivating, and helpful in improving their reading fluency, vocabulary, comprehension, and confidence.
5. Teachers regarded MORA as a practical, sustainable, and data-driven formative assessment tool, despite minor implementation challenges, supporting its integration into regular reading instruction.

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